

**THE ROLE OF PEDAGOGY AND PSYCHOLOGY IN THE
DEVELOPMENT OF IDEOLOGICAL IMMUNITY IN THE ERA OF THE
THIRD RENAISSANCE IN UZBEKISTAN**

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In recent years, the problem of ideological immunity has become more and more urgent all over the world, which, of course, makes us think about methods to eradicate this problem. All these reflections lead us to a certain question: "What is the essence of ideological immunity?" The main and first element of ideological immunity is knowledge. The second main part of the system of ideological immunity is the system of values formed on the basis of such knowledge.

Directly, each state is trying to ensure the safety of the population, to form a psychologically sound society, to protect the younger generation from negative external influences, as well as to strengthen the ideological immunity of the country's citizens.

An important role in the formation of the ideological immunity of the state is played by the work of domestic psychologists, whose job is to work out public consciousness.

Public consciousness is the spiritual side of society's life, acting in the form of ideas, thoughts, people's ideas about themselves (self-awareness), about events and phenomena of reality, about society as a whole (worldview). To a greater extent, at the moment, a struggle between more developed states is breaking out on the "great chessboard" – the world stage, as a result of which such methods as

information and psychological attacks are used. In turn, psychologists are obliged to take measures to protect society. In this regard, the psychology of the masses or the psychology of the crowd begins to speak.

The psychology of the masses (psychology of the crowd) is the peculiarities of the behavior and thinking of a large group of people with common views and feelings [2]. The psychology of the masses is concretized in a whole system of ideas, among which the following are especially significant:

1. A psychological crowd is not a collection of people in one place, but a human aggregate with a mental community.

2. The individual exists consciously, and the mass, the crowd – unconsciously, because consciousness is individual, and the unconscious is collective.

3. Crowds are conservative, despite their revolutionary way of doing things. They end up restoring what they first overthrew, because for them, as for all those who are in a state of hypnosis, the past is much more important than the present.

4. The masses, the crowds, need the support of a leader who captivates them with his hypnotizing authority, and not with arguments of reason and not submission to force. Propaganda (or communication) has an irrational basis. Thanks to this, obstacles standing in the way of action are overcome. Since in most cases our actions are the result of beliefs, then a critical mind, lack of conviction and passion interfere with actions. Such hindrances can be eliminated with the help of hypnotic, propagandistic suggestion, and therefore propaganda addressed to the masses should use an energetic and imaginative language of allegories with simple and imperative formulations.

5. In order to control the masses (party, class, nation, etc.), politics must be based on some higher idea (revolution, Homeland, etc.), which is introduced and nurtured in the minds of people. As a result of such suggestion, it turns into collective images and actions [2].

A person, uniting in groups with other people, makes up a society. But, before

the formation of this society, the personality itself is formed as a result of its life path. The greatest influence is exerted by the system of education and the work of teachers, psychologists in the formation of a psychologically sound personality.

As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyoyev said: "The greatest wealth is intelligence and science, the greatest inheritance is good upbringing, the greatest poverty is lack of knowledge.

Indeed, the new Renaissance, the foundation of which we are laying with pure thoughts and high hopes, will contribute to the creation of such huge wealth in the country, ensuring a decent life for the people and the formation of an invaluable heritage for future generations"[1].

Thanks to the proper education of young people, the country can provide society with ideological immunity, which is based on the spirit of patriotism, moral and ethical principles, a well-formed personality structure, psychological assistance provided to the entire population.

Based on the above data, we conducted a social survey among university students aged 18 to 25 years.

The main topics of the survey were:

- 1) The role of the profession of a teacher and psychologist in the formation of modern society.
- 2) Disclosure of the term "ideological immunity".
- 3) Ways to provide society with "ideological immunity" in the era of the III Renaissance in Uzbekistan.

Comparing the answers of the male and female sides, we came to the conclusion that the gender difference did not have a big impact on the results of the study, which cannot be said about the age criterion. Students of the age category from 18 to 20 years old replied that at the moment, thanks to the media, they watch short psychological videos daily, and also that the literature on the subject of "psychology" is of interest to the younger generation, as it "teaches them to love themselves, life and prepares them for adult independent life, giving them self-

confidence and giving them motivation to achieve their intended goal." Most of the students were familiar with the term "ideological immunity" and already had a primary idea of what it really was. They replied that this immunity develops as a result of the enrichment of the spiritual, cultural and moral-ethical components of the personality. In addition, they supplemented their answers with the fact that people with a broader outlook are less prone to ideological threats and attacks of any kind.

Students aged 21 and older answered dryly, relying on a purely personal opinion, expressed themselves as follows: "The role of teachers and psychologists is to provide psychological assistance to people with any mental injuries, strengthen the family system, as well as contribute to the formation of society by working on personality. They also know the concept of "ideological immunity", but thanks to the media. As for ensuring the immunity of the state, the best method of protecting the state from potential threats is the promotion of a reliable and bright future by government agencies, speeches by the President addressed to the people, etc."

As our social research has shown, students are familiar with the concepts of "potential threat", "ideological immunity", they also have their own subjective opinion and views on the ideology of society as a whole.

Based on the answers, we found out that the profession of a teacher and a psychologist is recognized among students and is advanced in shaping society and the way to eliminate "ideological threats" is to enrich the spiritual, moral, cultural and historical view of the individual, through education and stimulation by government authorities.

As the head of the country said: "The systems of preschool, school, higher and secondary special education, scientific and cultural institutions are four interconnected links of the future Renaissance. We consider kindergarten teachers, school teachers, professors and teachers, scientific and creative intelligentsia to be the four most important pillars in shaping the era of the new Renaissance" [1].

Thus, the development of Russian pedagogy and psychology directly affects the protection of the entire society of the country, as well as provides it with ideological immunity. Thanks to the coordinated work of teachers and psychologists, the citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan at the time of the Third Renaissance are building a highly organized spiritual and cultural society, which undoubtedly gives great hopes for the future of the whole country.

Literature:

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